

First record of host plant for *Cogia stylites* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) (Hesperiidae: Eudaminae)

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Abstract: This paper reports the butterfly *Cogia stylites* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) feeding on a Fabaceae tree species in Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil. The immature specimen was found inside its shelter, constructed using leaflets from the host plant identified as *Senna multijuga* subsp. *lindleyana* var. *lindleyana* (Gardner) H.S. Irwin & Barneby (Fabaceae: Caesalpinioideae). Other species of *Cogia* Butler, 1870, and the closely related genus *Typhedanus* Butler, 1870, have a specific relationship with plants of the genus *Senna* Mill. Thus, this is the first report of *C. stylites* feeding on *Senna* Mill. species.

Keywords: Fabaceae, Lepidoptera, *Senna*, shelter, *Typhedanina*, *Typhedanus*

Introduction

The taxonomic history of the butterfly species *Cogia stylites* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) began when Herrich-Schäffer (1869) described it as *Eudamus stylites*, later transferred to *Thymele* Fabricius, 1807 (Kirby, 1871), *Goniurus* Hübner, [1819] (Plötz, 1881), *Urbanus* Hübner, [1819] (William & Hayward, 1944), *Typhedanus* Butler, 1870 (Evans, 1952), *Chioides* Lindsey, 1921 (Zikán & Zikán, 1968), and more recently, to *Cogia* Butler, 1870 (Li et al., 2019). Schaus (1902) described *Eudamus janita* based on specimens from Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, now synonymised under the name *Cogia stylites* by Evans (1952).

This Neotropical species inhabits the Atlantic Forest in Southeast and the South Regions of Brazil

(Schaus, 1902; Evans, 1952; Zikán & Zikán, 1968; O. Mielke & Casagrande, 1997; Brown & Freitas, 2000; Bonfanti et al., 2011; Pérez et al., 2017), and also has records for Panama, Colombia (Godman & Salvin, 1893), Guyana (Shambu & Nankishore, 2018), French Guiana (Evans, 1952), and Ecuador (William & Hayward, 1944). However, the occurrence of *C. stylites* in these countries is still doubtful, and may be due to misidentification. Most Neotropical Eudaminae are known by feeding mainly on Fabaceae species (Beccaloni et al., 2008; Warren et al., 2009), however, despite the amount of information regarding host plant associations with this subfamily, this is poorly known for *C. stylites*, and there is no record of immature stages or host plants. Thus, this study presents for the first time part of the immature stage and the host plant record for *C. stylites*.

Material and methods

In November 2024, a final instar larva of *C. stylites* was found inside its shelter on a Fabaceae tree species in Curitiba (25°27'05.1"S 49°14'29.0"W, 895 m a.s.l.), Paraná, Brazil. This larva was brought to the laboratory to record emergence of the adult and confirm the species. The terminology of pupa stage follows Scoble (1992). The specimen was identified through Evans (1952) and deposited in Entomological

Collection Padre Jesus Santiago Moure (DZUP), Zoology Department, Universidade Federal do Paraná (UFPR), Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil. Branches with flowers from the host plant were sent to UPCB Herbarium at the Universidade Federal do Paraná for exsiccate deposition. The plant identification was carried out by the specialist Prof. Dr Roseli Lopes da Costa Bortoluzzi from the Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina (UDESC), Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil.

Fig 1. (A) Multi-leaf shelter built by the immature of *Cogia stylites* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) (Hesperiidae: Eudaminae) on *Senna multijuga* subsp. *lindleyana* var. *lindleyana* (Gardner) H.S. Irwin & Barneby (Fabaceae: Caesalpinioideae), red arrow pointing to the pupa. Pupa: (B) dorsal, (C) lateral, and (D) ventral views.

Fig 2. *Cogia stylites* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) (Hesperiidae: Eudaminae) DZ 56.359, female: (A) dorsal and (B) ventral views. Scale bar = 1 cm.

Table 1. Host plants of *Cogia* Butler, 1870 and *Typhedanus* Butler, 1870 species and their respective locality of interaction, followed by its reference.

Species/Subspecies	Host plant	Country	Reference
<i>Cogia caicus caicus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869)	<i>Acacia angustissima</i> (Mill.) Kuntze ¹	Mexico	Kendall & McGuire (1975) / Scott (1986)
<i>Cogia calchas</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869)	<i>Mimosa albida</i> Humb. & Bonpl. Ex Willd. ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Mimosa camporum</i> Benth. ¹	Costa Rica	
	<i>Mimosa candollei</i> R. Grether ¹	Costa Rica	
	<i>Mimosa pigra</i> L. ¹	United States, Mexico, Costa Rica	Scott (1986) / Harley et al. (1995) / Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. ¹	Trinidad, Costa Rica	Cock (1991) / Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Mimosa quadrivalvis</i> L. ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Mimosa skinneri</i> Benth. ¹	Costa Rica	
	<i>Mimosa xanthocentra</i> Mart. ¹	Costa Rica	
		<i>Indigofera</i> L. ¹	Brazil
		Argentina	
	<i>Mimosa</i> L. ¹	Brazil	
<i>Cogia crameri</i> (McHenry, 1960)	<i>Senna chrysocarpa</i> (Desv.) H.S. Irwin & Barneby ¹	Brazil	Moss (1949)
<i>Cogia hiska hiska</i> Evans, 1953	<i>Acaciella villosa</i> (Sw.) Britton & Rose ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
<i>Cogia hippalus hippalus</i> (W. H. Edwards, 1882)	<i>Acacia</i> Mill. ¹	Mexico	Glassberg (2007)
<i>Cogia outis</i> (Skinner, 1894)	<i>Acacia texensis</i> Torr. & A. Gray ¹	United States	Scott (1986)
	<i>Acacia angustissima</i> ¹		
<i>Cogia stylites</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869)	<i>Senna multijuga</i> subsp. <i>lindleyana</i> var. <i>lindleyana</i> (Gardner) H.S. Irwin & Barneby ¹	Brazil	This study

Table 1 continued...

<i>Cogia undulatus</i> (Hewitson, 1867)	<i>Mimosa skinneri</i> ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb. ¹	Brazil	Moss (1949)
	<i>Senna cobanensis</i> (Britton) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Senna hayesiana</i> (Britton) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹		
	<i>Senna corymbosa</i> (Lam.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Argentina	Hayward (1969)
	<i>Senna obtusifolia</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Brazil, Trinidad, Mexico, Costa Rica	Silva et al. (1968) / Cock & Evans (1984) / Palmer & Pullen (2001) / Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link ¹	Brazil	Moss (1949) / Silva et al. (1968)
	<i>Senna pallida</i> (Vahl) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Senna papillosa</i> (Britton) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Costa Rica	
	<i>Senna reticulata</i> (Willd.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Brazil	Moss (1949)
	<i>Senna uniflora</i> (Willd.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Brazil	Silva et al. (1968)
	<i>Zea mays</i> L.*	Venezuela	Beccaloni et al. (2008)
<i>Typhedanus ampyx</i> (Godman & Salvin, 1893)	<i>Senna atomaria</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)
	<i>Senna pallida</i> (Vahl) H.S.Irwin & Barneby ¹	Costa Rica	
<i>Typhedanus cajeta eluina</i> (Godman & Salvin, 1894)	<i>Senna obtusifolia</i> ¹	Costa Rica	Janzen et al. (1998)
	<i>Senna pallida</i> ¹		
	<i>Mimosa skinneri</i> Benth. ¹		Janzen & Hallwachs (2009)

¹Fabaceae, *Poaceae

Results and discussion

The last instar larva built a multi-leaf shelter, as classified by Greeney (2009) (Fig. 1A) using many small leaflets to cover itself. According to Greeney, this type of shelter is built during the last instar, particularly when the leaves are divided into leaflets, which forces the fully-grown larva to use multiple leaves to cover itself completely. This immature remained until it turned into pupa. Here is the description of the pupa (Fig. 1B–D) – entirely brownish, without setae; prothorax, mesothorax, and metathorax more brownish than the abdominal segments; prothorax with a pair of false eyes; abdominal segments light brown with several black spots; two last abdominal segments dark brown. The adult emerged two weeks later (Fig. 2), and confirmed as *C. stylites* (DZ 56.359).

The host plant was identified as *Senna multijuga* subsp. *lindleyana* var. *lindleyana* (Gardner) H.S. Irwin & Barneby (Fabaceae: Caesalpinioideae) (107238). There are records of seven other *Cogia* species feeding on Fabaceae, but apparently only *C. undulatus* (Hewitson, 1867) and *C. crameri* (McHenry, 1960) have a specific relationship with *Senna* species (Moss, 1949; Hayward, 1969; Silva et al., 1968; Cock & Evans, 1984; Palmer & Pullen, 2001; Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009), as well as some members of *Typhedanus* (Janzen et al., 1998; Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009) (Table 1), a closely related genus in Typhedanina Grishin, 2019. Probably, these species feeding on these Fabaceae genera listed here built a multi-leaf shelter during the last's instars of development, when the immature is larger than the leaves.

This paper is the first report of *Cogia stylites* feeding on *Senna multijuga*, illustrating the pupa of this species collected in the South of Brazil, and providing an overview of the host plants to some species of *Cogia* and *Typhedanus*.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Dra. Marília Locatelli Corrêa for preparing the exsiccate and depositing at the UPCB Herbarium, Botanic Department, at the Universidade Federal do Paraná (UFPR). We also thank Prof. Dr Roseli Lopes da Costa Bortoluzzi from the Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina (UDESC) for identifying the host plant. Finally, we thank the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) for the fellowships to the first (88887.949958 / 2024-00), second (88887.931876 / 2024-00), third (88887.931875 / 2024-00), and fourth (88887.693997 / 2022-00) authors. Additionally, the authors thank the reviewers for their valuable suggestions.

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